

DATA COLLECTION

To properly organise collection of samples in order to detect and isolate *Brucella canis* strains, following metadata are considered as essential for epidemiological analyses as well as tracing of suspicions, outbreaks and infection sources, as well as development of early warning systems.

- List of metadata to be collected:

type of sample,
sample description,
dog origins,
host breed,
reproductive status,

canine contacts,
human contacts,
storage conditions,
transport conditions,
country,

region of collection,
city,
commune,
latitude, longitude,
additional comments.

- [Data base example](#)
- Epidemiological questionnaire: [Model 1](#), [Model 2](#)
- PADI Web (under construction)
- Sample collection from live dogs:

Both	Females	Males
Blood in Citrate tube	Vaginal swab	Urine
Blood in EDTA tube	Aborted tissues	Semen (if not castrated)
Blood in dry tube	Miscarried foetuses	Preputial swab
Synovial liquids		

